

Brand Hate: One Decade of Research A Systematic Review

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Abstract: The purpose of this article is to comprehensively review of the complex phenomenon of brand hate. We aim to consolidate existing knowledge on brand hate by examining its nature, antecedents, outcomes, management strategies, and the personality traits of brand haters. A systematic review of brand hate literature is conducted, focusing on identifying the key triggers of brand hate, which include negative experiences, ideological mismatches, and symbolic incongruence. The review also delves into the behavioral consequences of brand hate, such as brand avoidance, brand switching, negative word-of-mouth, and brand retaliation. Methodological approaches used in brand hate research, including surveys, qualitative methods, mixed methods, and experiments, are discussed, providing a comprehensive overview of the research designs employed. Furthermore, the theoretical frameworks and models applied to analyze brand hate, such as the triangular theory of hate and self-congruity theory, are examined. The review reveals that brand hate is a multifaceted concept with various triggers and behavioral outcomes. It also highlights the prevalence of survey-based research methodologies in this field. The review sheds light on the theoretical foundations that underpin brand hate research and presents a comprehensive picture of the existing knowledge. This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge on brand hate by synthesizing key findings and underlining gaps in the literature. It emphasizes the importance of conducting cross-cultural and cross-industry studies and adopting machine learning-based methodologies in future research. Additionally, the review underscores the significance of brand hate management strategies and their implications for brand practitioners. This review offers both a roadmap for future research and practical insights for brand management in the context of brand hate.

Keywords: Brand hate, anti-consumption, anti-brand, consumer psychology, consumer behavior, consumer-brand relationship

1. Introduction

Brand hate is described as the most harmful and intense emotion towards a brand if the antecedents of brand hate can be understood and addressed there will be no need to deal with brand hate feelings and behavior in the first instance. As topic, brand hate is of interest to both researchers and practitioners. The last decade the research stream has seen a steady increase in the number of publications related to negative consumers-brand relationships in general and to brand hate in particular, which demonstrates the interest in practitioners and researchers. The concept of brand hate argues that consumers have negative primary emotions such disgust and anger towards brand.

According to Kucuk [1] brand hate is “Consumer detachment and aversion from a brand and its value systems as a result of constantly happening brand injustices that leads to intense and deeply held negative consumer emotions; A compound of emotions of disgust, contempt and anger leading to formation of seven types of brand hatreds”. As internal state, brand hate is harmful for brands, it leads to different negative reaction towards such as brand avoidance [2] brand retaliation [3] brand switching [4], negative WOM [5] and brand boycott [6]. On keen observation, it can be assumed that brand hate troublesome companies, especially today with the emergence of social media and the democratization of the market [7].

Marketers have already recognized the damage of brand hate specifically with the multiplication of anti-brands communities [8-11]. Despite the importance of brand hate phenomenon, considering the its significance in ruining brand equity [12], the literature related to this concept remained limited until the seminal – implicit-work of Grégoire, et al. [13] and Krishnamurthy and Kucuk [10].

Since then, scholars and marketers has shown a big amount of interest to advance this stream of research. Therefore, this increasing number of articles dealing with brand hate are also creating a conceptual confusion [14]. Starting from this statement, its crucial to revisit the pertinent literature related to this phenomenon [15].

The current paper aims to systematically review the literature related to brand hate by examining the relevant studies. In particular, we are addressing the following research questions:

- What are the emergent themes of brand hate literature?
- What are the key theories used in brand hate literature?
- What are the methodologies, methods and instruments used to investigate brand hate?
- Which contexts are examined in brand hate literature?

After the current introduction, a brief background of brand hate will be exposed. Second, we will present the methodology used for this systematic review. Third, we will present the thematic analysis which illustrates the distribution of brand hate literature per themes. Fourth, we will focus on theories, methodologies and methods used in brand hate literature. Fifth, a conceptual model will be presented as synthesis of the current state of art. Finally, this paper presents the conclusion section where the research agenda will be discussed.

2. Background

According to Kucuk [1] hate is the farthest edge of negative human emotions. Majority of social psychologists describe hate as secondary emotion, which a mix of other primary emotions such as anger, disgust, and hostility. In this spirit, Sternberg and Sternberg [16] consider hate as a triangular structure composed of disgust and repulsion, fear and anger. Conforming to the same theory, the emotion of hate is complex, and we can distinguish between seven types of hate. In other hand, brand hate can be defined as the most negative emotion that consumer can feel towards a brand [17]. In more detailed conceptualization, in agreement with the theory previously mentioned, brand hate is “*Consumer detachment and aversion from a brand and its value systems as a result of constantly happening brand injustices that leads to intense and deeply held negative consumer emotions; A compound of emotions of disgust, contempt and anger leading to formation of seven types of brand hatreds*” [1]. This second conceptualization is often used by scholars [18].

The growth of research related to brand hate construct is due to the emergence of the new stream of research named consumer-brand relationships initiated by Levy [19] and developed by the seminal work of Aaker and Biel [20] and Fournier [21]. In contrast to transitional perspective, relational paradigm states that consumers go beyond the functional product attributes by giving brand humanlike characteristics [22]. Fournier [21] highlighted that these relationships are analogous to interpersonal relationships.

Unlike other constructs such as brand love which has been empirically tested in 90’s [22], brand hate did not catch the attention of researchers, even that neuroscientists revealed that people tend to recall and share negative events more and easier than positive event. Kucuk [1] believes that this lack of research into brand hate in particular or negative emotions in general is due to the nature of human, including researchers, to ignore negative emotions.

The digitalization/the democratization of the market increase consumer empowerment. In fact, the anonymity and non-face-to-face communications introduced by the internet, consumers channel their true feelings, which was quit impossible to identify in offline channel [23]. Since then, hateful behaviors such as anti-branding activism became easier to detect [10] and the construct of brand hate started getting the attention of researchers. Grégoire, et al. [13] is one of the early scholars to implicitly conceptualizing brand hate. In their work, the authors found that consumers emotions towards brands can turn from love to hate which leads to brand avoidance and consumer revenge. In the same spirit, Krishnamurthy and Kucuk [10] initiated the concept of “Negative Double Jeopardy” which indicates that brand who attracts more lovers attracts more haters involved on anti-branding activism.

After these two founding articles related to brand hate, various perspectives, theories and methodologies have emerged to study the phenomenon [18] which provide some useful insights and also generated a conceptual confusion. It would be interesting to note that brand hate has been seen as a construct that is unidimensional [2, 17] to a construct that has several dimensions [4, 23, 24].

3. Methodology

Originated in medical science, the systematic literature review is a process that has been widely adopted in other fields to generate practical knowledge [25]. The primary aim of this process is to gather a vast amount of literature and produce a practical summary that can be acted upon. [26]. To this end, establishing and explicating a clear paper selection protocol is required [25, 27].

To address the previous research questions and ensure the methodological rigor conforming to the systematic review, we followed a clear process of inclusion/exclusion criteria. In this sense, we used the most widely used databases in social sciences which are Scopus and Web Of Science. This latter, according to Archambault, et al. [28], has the most reliable, with high impact, scientific studies, while Chirici [29] advanced that Web of Science offers various information. Scopus, in contrario, contains 59% of journals and 63% of

articles, when Web of Science has only 35% and 40%, respectively. We utilized "brand hate" as a search keyword. Despite a wealth of information on brand hate in textbooks, consulting reports, and academic theses, we limited our research to peer-reviewed journal articles.

According to pre-decided criteria (See Table 1), all the papers were read by both the authors independently. At the end of this process, we merged the articles founded in both databases while removing the duplicates articles. A total of 75 articles full-text papers from the merged database using the aforementioned keyword. Then, we created a dataset that included fields such as Journal, publication year, utilized theories, methodology, analysis techniques, key variables, sample size, etc.

Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion criteria used in articles selection

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Peer-reviewed journal articles indexed in Scopus and Web of Science databases between 2012-2022	Conferences papers
Articles in English language	Thesis and Master thesis
Articles with the main focus in brand Hate (Brand hate in title and/or brand as keyword)	Professional Reports

4. Thematic content analysis

After paper selection process, literature was categorized by both authors independently based on content similarity. These classifications were later compared and merged to one thematic content analysis. At the end, we devised the literature to the following themes and sub-themes:

- 1. Brand hate nature:** this border theme covers three sub-themes: "Conceptualization of brand hate", "Antecedents of brand hate" and "Consequences of brand hate".
- 2. Brand hate in corporate context:** This border theme encompasses three sub-themes : "brand hate in different countries", "brand hate in industries" and "brand hate in luxury"
- 3. Brand hate outside the corporate context:** This border theme covers three sub-themes: "Political brand hate", "Sports brand hate" and "Destination brand hate";
- 4. Brand hate management and haters personality:** This border theme encompasses "brand hate in dynamic perspective", "Strategies to deal with brand hate" and "Haters traits personality";

The subsequent section presents the principal discoveries of the papers categorized under each theme.

4.1. Brand hate nature

Emotion is defined as "a complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioral and physiological elements by which an individual attempts to deal with a personally significant matter or event." [18]. Emotions are classified into two categories, as Plutchik and Kellerman [30] highlight emotions are either primary or secondary. The former can be described as reactions to external events to the extent that certain triggering events can make you feel emotions, while the latter occurs when you feel something about the emotion itself.

4.1.1. Conceptualization of brand hate

In branding literature, brand hate is conceptualized as an emotion. Some authors as Bryson, et al. [17], Hegner, et al. [2], Kucuk [31] and Sarkar, et al. [32] consider brand hate as unidimensional emotion. While the majority of authors [4, 23, 24, 33, 34] consider brand hate as multi-dimensional construct. These conceptual differences are due to the theoretical framework used to explain the phenomenon disused bellow.

In order to clarify the conceptual differences between these two schools of thoughts, we will illustrate it with definitions. Bryson, et al. [17] believes that brand hate is the most negative emotion that consumer can feel towards a brand while Kucuk [1] define brand hate as "Consumer detachment and aversion from a brand and its value systems as a result of constantly happening brand injustices that leads to intense and deeply held negative consumer emotions; A compound of emotions of disgust, contempt and anger leading to formation of seven types of brand hatreds".

According to the multi-dimensional conceptualization, multiple taxonomies of brand hate are presented in the literature. These typologies are based on the theoretical background mobilized to explain the phenomenon. In this vein, we can present two taxonomies. In one hand, Zarantonello, et al. [34] present two different types of brand hate: (a) active brand hate which is a component of brand hate that includes emotions such as anger and contempt/disgust towards a brand. It is defined as the purposeful and deliberate intention to avoid or reject a brand, or even to act out behaviors that demonstrate this rejection; (b) passive brand hate which is component of brand hate that includes emotions related to fear, disappointment, shame, and dehumanization towards a brand. In other hand, Fetscherin [4], Kucuk [23] extrapolated the triangular theory of hate of

Sternberg and Sternberg [16] developed initially to explain interpersonal hate to consumer brand relationship. They conclude that consumer can experience seven types of brand hate as discussed below.

a) Mild Brand hate

Mild hate is the first level of brand hate. It comprises three basic types of brand hate: cold brand hate, cool brand hate, and hot brand hate.

1) Cold brand hate

The triangular theory of hate [16] states that cold hate is characterized by unworthy thoughts directed at the target. In terms of basic emotions, it can be expressed through devaluation/diminution of the target. In the branding context, "The hater tries to distance himself/herself from the hated brand, its associations, and followers" [1].

2) Cool brand hate

Cool hate, referring to the triangular theory of hate [16], is a negation of intimacy towards the targeted person or group. Emotionally speaking, it involves the emotion of disgust. A consumer who feels cool brand hate experiences dark emotions such as "repulsion, resentment, revolt, and finally disgust toward a disliked brand" [1]. In terms of behavioral outcomes, the consumer tries not only to distance himself [1] from the brand but also switches to another brand [4].

3) Hot brand hate

Hot hate, conferring to the triangular theory of hate [16], is manifested through extreme feelings of anger. Some author as Beck [35], refers to this kind of hate as "hot, reactive violence" [16]. The extrapolation of the concept in the branding context holds. Kucuk [1] advances that "Feelings of extreme anger and anxiety toward a brand are represented in hot brand hate" [1]. Fetscherin [4] found that hot brand hate leads to the "willingness to make financial sacrifices to hurt the brand."

b) Medium brand hate

As mentioned in the figure above, medium brand hate is the second category of brand hate. It included the combination of two primary brand hate types. Medium brand hate includes simmering brand hate, seething brand hate, and boiling brand hate.

1) Simmering brand hate

In interpersonal relationships, simmering hate is "characterized by feelings of loathing toward the hated target." [16]. In the branding context, it combines disgust and contempt [4]. Regarding behavioral outcomes, simmering brand hate leads to private complaining [4].

2) Seething brand hate

Sternberg and Sternberg [16] noted, "Seething hate is characterized by feelings of revilement toward the targeted individual or individuals." It's composed of cold and hot hate. In consumer brand relationships, seething brand hate is translated to brand revenge [4].

3) Boiling brand hate

Psychology literature underlines that "boiling hate is characterized by feelings of revulsion toward the target" [16], while marketing literature states that boiling brand hate is composed of cool and hot hate [1]. In addition, it has been shown that boiling hate in brand-consumer relationship leads to brand retaliation in the short term [4].

c) Severe brand hate: Burning brand hate

Burning brand hate is a severe level of brand hate. Sternberg and Sternberg [16] name it metaphorically "Need for annihilation" to describe it in interpersonal relationships. It's composed of essential components of hate. [1] states that burning brand hate indicates the "severe and ultimate level brand hate." In the branding context, Burning brand hate leads to two different outcomes: Public complaining and brand revenge [4].

Lately, Zhang and Laroche [24] developed another taxonomy of brand hate, which consist of three types of brand hate : (a) anger-related brand hate which characterized by aggressive emotions such as anger, annoyance, furiousness, and rage. This type of brand hate is associated with events that are appraised as harmful and frustrating, which can make people feel like they want to explode. People who experience anger-related brand hate may feel a strong sense of disgust towards the brand; (b) Sadness-related brand hate which is

characterized by emotions such as helplessness, hopelessness, disappointment, and depression; and (c) Fear-related which is characterized by emotions such as confusion, shock, weirdness, oddity, scariness, and frightfulness. People who experience this kind of brand hate may feel scared or frightened by the brand.

4.1.2. Antecedents Of brand hate

An antecedent is “*the reason for a specific feeling and triggers a specific behavior*” [14]. In our systematic review, antecedents are the main focus of researchers with 41 journal articles out of 71 with a ratio of 58%. The reason of such interest is its empirical or actionable outcomes to prevent brand hate, according to Kucuk [14] “*if the antecedents of brand hate can be understood and addressed there will be no need to deal with brand hate feelings and behavior in the first instance.*” [14].

a) Negative Past Experience

Lee, et al. [36] advance that negative past experience is related to undelivered brand promises resulting in unmet expectations, an unpleasant store environment, or poor brand performance [37]. According to the self-congruity theory [38, 39], negative past experience is conceptualized as a functional incongruence. Sirgy, et al. [39] define functional congruence as “*the match between the beliefs of the product’s utilitarian attributes (performance-related) and the audience’s referent attributes.*” Regarding expectation-disconfirmation theory [40], consumer satisfaction is a matter of confirmation of primary expectations. According to the avoidance model of Lee, et al. [36], when consumers perceive that additional value factors are unfulfilled and not matched with actual expectations, they become unsatisfied and subsequently avoid brands.

Assumed the multidimensionality of the past experience, scholars have focused on the critical elements of this experience. Islam, et al. [41] provided these elements and their impact on brand hate. Their study shows functional incongruence is linked with product quality and other factors such as ambient, design, and social aspects. In the same vein, Roy, et al. [8] discussed negative experience in terms of sensory, affective, behavioral, and intellectual experiences.

Negative past experiences can be defined as violating of consumer expectations [34]. As explained by Lee, et al. [36] and Hegner, et al. [2], negative experiences occur when a brand's actual performance is below expectations, likely resulting in dissatisfaction. We should also highlight that is that a negative experience with a particular product of a brand affects attitudes towards other products from the same brand name, and, thus, hate gets generalized on a brand level [2].

Fournier [21] used the term “*un- imaginable experience*” and advanced that it could lead to negative emotions towards brands. Our systematic review results indicates that negative past experience is the most determinant used to explain brand hate. In this spirit, multiple studies found a positive direct relationship between negative past experience and brand hate (Bryson, et al. [17], Zarantonello, et al. [34], Hegner, et al. [2], Platania, et al. [42], Kucuk [31], Hashim and Kasana [43], Islam, et al. [41], Yang and Mundel [44], Kazmi, et al. [45], Islam, et al. [46], Banerjee and Goel [47], Sarkar, et al. [32], Nguyen [37], Pinto and Brandão [48], Rodrigues, et al. [9], Bryson, et al. [49], Joshi and Yadav [50], Costa and Azevedo [5], Jabeen, et al. [51], Roy, et al. [8], Gois, et al. [52]).

According to Kucuk [23], negative past experience “*can also be associated with transactional disagreements between consumer and company*” and it leads to injustice in the eye of consumer. He added that negative past experience (unlike other antecedents) requires that the consumer is an active/direct relationship with the brand.

b) Symbolic Incongruence

Symbolic congruence as construct has its roots in self-congruity theory [38, 39]. Marketing literature has found that consumers choose brands that are align with their identity [43]. Conversely, they reject brands that symbolically do not align with their identity, which is known as symbolic incongruence. Unlike the first antecedent delivered from a transactional perspective, symbolic congruence is central to postmodern theories. According to Elliott [53] “*consumers no longer consume products for their material utilities but consume the symbolic meaning of those products as portrayed in their images*”.

In negative consumer-brand relationship, symbolic incongruence occurs “*when brand does not truly represent itself in accordance with the consumers’ image*” [43]. Consumer image in other hand refers to the self-concept. According to Sirgy, et al. [39] self-concept is the totality of the individual’s thoughts and feelings having reference to himself as an object. Referring to the dis-identification theory, Lee, et al. [36] suggests that consumers may develop their self-concept by dis-identifying with brands that are perceived to be inconsistent with their own image.

Multiple studies found that these discrepancies between the symbolic meanings of a brand and the consumer’s sense of self leads to negative emotions and behaviors [41] such as brand avoidance [36] and brand

hate [2, 5, 9, 34, 41-43, 45, 46, 48, 52, 54].

Kucuk [14] highlight that “In identity-based brand hate situations, consumers are mostly not active users of the hated brand, in fact, the consumer has often never purchased the brand.”

c) Ideological incompatibility

Consumption as an economic act is not only related to the functional benefits or the symbolic meanings. One of the alternative definitions of brands is advanced by Lee, et al. [36] “A brand is a constellation of values”. This set of values and beliefs is widely used notion in consumer research and business ethics as brand ideology. According to Crockett and Wallendorf [55] brand ideology plays a relevant role, from a cognitive perspective, in consumer brand choice. It refers to brand shared values and beliefs in terms of societal, religious, political, and morally unethical behavior [9].

Ideological incompatibility arises where there is a mismatch between consumers beliefs and the brand perceived ideology [2]. It occurs to a situation where “Companies that are not acting accordingly with the consumer’s perceptions regarding moral, legal and social issues” Hashim and Kasana [43]. In contrast to the previous determinants, ideological incompatibility goes beyond the utilitarian benefits and the symbolic meaning of the consumption and focus on moral and societal issues [46]. In a macro level, ideological incompatibility is related to the anti-consumption paradigm [36]. In terms of consumer-brand relationships, previous research found a positive relationship between brand hate and ideological incompatibility.

Kucuk [14] advance that ideological incompatibility and the symbolic incongruence are different constructs and they “lead to different types of brand hate and different types of hate outcomes”.

d) Subjective norms and brand embarrassment

According to the theory of planned behavior [56], subjective norms represent an intrinsic desire to act in a way that others (close environment) would approve of. This “others” refers to the family and friends. Traditional marketing literature established the role of subjective norms on purchase intentions, brand love, brand loyalty, positive online reviews and brand judgement overall [57].

From an opposite point of view, negative subjective norms can lead to negative emotions/behaviors. For example, Lee, et al. [36] found that brand avoidance is motivated by dissociative reference groups. In the same spirit, Sharma, et al. [57] concluded that “Individuals are known to avoid brands that are not accepted by their circle of influence”. In emotional level, scholars found that subjective norms lead to brand hate [50, 57]. In contrast to ideological mismatch, subjective norms arise from the circle of influence and not from the ideological set of the consumer himself.

If subjective norms can lead to brand hate without consuming certain brand, the opposite case can occur. Sarkar, et al. [32] refers to it as brand embarrassment that occurs “when an individual feels that he/she has made an incompatible projection of himself or herself in front of others present in a social establishment, where the principle of compatibility is considered to be important”. It’s a *posteriori*, a confrontation to subjective norms. Sarkar, et al. [32] found a positive link between brand embarrassment and brand hate towards a Tata, which is a nano-car with a image related to a poor man in India.

e) Lack of uniqueness

Brand hate literature established the impact of lack of brand uniqueness leads to consumer brand hate [9, 12, 58, 59]. Various studies presented multiple constructs around this lack of uniqueness. Rodrigues, et al. [9] advanced that brand inauthenticity leads to brand hate. According to their paper, scholars shows that less authentic brands fail to establish a stronger emotional attachment with a brand compared to highly authentic brands. This brand inauthenticity implies two faces : (a) the brand promise does not stem from its core values and (b) brand actions are perceived as non-authentic by consumers, since the brand promise was not fulfilled in an individual, continuous and consistent manner [60]. Another construct is related to the similarity to the competitor [12, 58]. When a consumer use or select brand, he has an inherent desire to increase the sense of individuality and inclusiveness [58]. In an opposite situation, similarity to competitor offer generates a feeling of unwantedness, generating negative emotions such as brand hate. Another construct can be fall under the same category is brand jealousy. It occurs when a brand became too popular and mainstream, thus consumer start to experience negative emotions where other consumers start using the same brand. This construct joins the previous construct where consumer start losing his sense of inclusiveness and his sense of possessiveness over the brand. Kashif, et al. [59] found that brand jealousy leads to luxury brand hate. Overall, this lack of uniqueness, can be viewed in terms of Snob effect which indicates “when status sensitive consumers come to reject a particular product as and when it is seen to be consumed by the general mass of people” [61]

f) Counter-effects of advertising

Advertising is a mechanism used by brands via paid media to spread information related to their offer [3]. Marketing literature has largely established the impact of advertising on brand equity. However, advertising can also lead to negative consequences for brands such as brand hate [3, 37, 51].

Nguyen [37] found that deceptive advertising motivate brand hate of Vietnamize netizens. Deceptive advertising refers to misleading advertising indicating the failures of one (or all) of following components: brand content, celebrity endorsers, music and responses. According to their theoretical framework, deceptive advertising is the most determinant of brand hate. In United States, Jabeen, et al. [51] found that overload advertising leads to the hatred towards food brands during covid-19. It refers to “*the negative experiences of the users of a brand on being inundated, overloaded, disturbed, and overwhelmed by the frequent promotional messages sent to them during the COVID-19 pandemic.*” [51]. Noor, et al. [3] found that muslim consumers in Pakistan experience brand hate if they perceive the brand’s publicity as offensive. According to Noor, et al. [3] “*offensive advertising comprises messages that breach customs, laws, morals or social codes of society.*”

g) Peer identification & stereotyping of the brand costumers

This antecedent is slightly similar to the identarian antecedent of brand hate. If consumers experience hatred towards a brand incoherent with their identity, they feel the same way if they perceive that consumers of certain brand are symbolically mismatching their identity. Brand hate literature suggest two distinct constructs in this level. Negative stereotypes which refer to “*consumers’ notion that they, through using a certain brand hold self-concepts similar to those of other consumers of the same brand*”[49]. According to their paper, Bryson, et al. [49] found a positive relationship between this negative stereotypes and luxury brand hate. The second construct is peer identification which can be defined as “*the extent of an individual’s identification with other of the same type of individuals associated with the organization*” [62]. Deriving from the social identity theory, it “*involves self-expansion of customer self, part of “who we are” as they become anchored in other customers.*” [11]. In united states context, Itani [11] found a positive link between peer identification and competitor brand hate.

h) Rumors & Negative Word-of-mouth

Negative word-of-mouth is “*informal, person-to-person communication between a perceived non-commercial communicator and a receiver regarding a brand, a product, an organization or a service.*” [63]. According to Bryson, et al. [49] can join subjective norms in shaping brand hate with the differences in terms of the closeness of the environment to the consumer. Lee, et al. [64] highlight that “*indications of consumers complying with peers’ perceived wishes rather than following situation specific, rational cues are thus signs of subjective group norms affecting individuals’ behavior*” [49]. During covid-19, Jabeen, et al. [51] found that hatred towards food brands is motivated by negative word-of-mouth, while Bryson, et al. [49] found a positive relationship between negative word-of-mouth and luxury brand hatred. Rumors, in the other side, use the same mechanism as negative word-of-mouth but in a macro level. According to Kapferer [65], rumors are the development and movement of information in a society without confirmation from official source. Marketing literature has largely highlight the role of rumors in destructing brand equity. Hashim and Kasana [43] found that rumors about fast food brands are the main determinant of brand hate.

i) Poor relationship quality & Perceived betrayal

Brand hate, as we mention before, is studied in lens of consumer-brand relationship [21]. If the quality of relationship is perceived as low, it can trigger negative emotions such hate towards a brand. The component of consumer-brand relationship are namely trust, satisfaction and commitment [46]. The lack in one (or all) of them leads to brand hate [43, 46]. This construct find its roots in both social exchange theory and triangular theory of hate [16]. Another construct join this is antecedent is the perceived betrayal. According the Nguyen and Nguyen [6], perceived betrayal is a breach in honoring an expected behavior or norm associated with trust. Like human relationship, when trust and commitment are not fulfilled, it leads to hate [6, 66]. The perceive betrayal, as antecedent, is harmful considering its ability to turn brand lovers to brand haters [13, 59].

4.1.3. Outcomes of brand hate

Hirschman [67] introduced the framework of “*voice vs exit*”, according to which customers have two options when they experience negative emotions towards a brand : they can either express their voice in order to remind the brand to improve the quality of their products and experiences or the can exit the relationship with the brand. In alternative and detailed model, Zarantonello, et al. [34] presented their framework “*avoidance, approach and attack*”. In brand hate literature, this framework “*sits on a stronger and broader conceptual ground*” [14].

a) Brand avoidance

According to Hegner, et al. [2], brand avoidance is a consumer behavior resulting from brand hate that refers to a situation where a consumers turn their backs to a targeted brand. Lee, et al. [36] indicates that brand avoidance is “*phenomenon whereby consumers deliberately choose to keep away from or reject a brand*”. Brand avoidance leads to non-consumption same as non-repurchase intention and brand switch. According to Fetscherin [4], brand avoidance is conceptually different from this latter, he highlight that “*It is only in the case of brand switching that a consumer turns into a non-consumer, whereas for brand avoidance this is not always the case. One could simply avoid a brand without ever having purchased it. In this respect, brand switching is one form of brand avoidance.*” However, we believe that non-repurchase intention, as construct, is different of brand avoidance. Curina, et al. [68] define non-repurchase intention as “*customers’ willingness to avoid another purchase from the same firm, based on their previous negative experiences.*” This definition implies an active consumer, which is not the necessarily the case of brand avoidance.

Multiple studies found that brand avoidance is a direct behavior of brand hate [2, 5, 8, 9, 24, 37, 45, 48, 51, 69].

b) Non-repurchase intention.

As we discussed before, non-repurchase intention share the same outcome as brand avoidance which is a non-consumption of brand. The only difference is the status of consumer regarding the brand which is “active consumer” [68]. In this spirit, Itani [11] conceptualize the purchase intention as the willingness of consumer to buy again from the same brand. Our systematic review results suggest that brand hate leads to non-repurchase intention in services context [68], while competitor brand hate leads to repurchase intention [11].

c) Brand switching

Unlike brand avoidance and non-repurchase intention, brand switching is not a simple behavior of avoiding or non-repurchase intention of the same brand , it refers to “*consumers would be inclined to switch to an alternative service provider.*” [8]. According the Fetscherin [4], “disgust brand-hate” leads to brand switching, while Islam, et al. [46] found a positive link between App hate and brand switching. Roy, et al. [8], in their turn, concluded that hatred towards American brands leads to brand switching.

d) Negative word-of-mouth, private and public complaining

Kucuk [1] argue that consumers have tendency to share the negative experiences more that positive ones. This share of negative experiences with a brand is known as negative word-of-mouth that refers to negative “*unofficial advice among consumers*” [70]. It is an alert to others consumers about their negative experiences [2]. Islam, et al. [46] explain that negative word-of-mouth can be considered as “indirect revenge” towards the brand. Negative word-of-mouth can be classified into two kinds : on the first hand, when consumer is talking negatively about a brand to his friends or family we use the term private complaining [2]. According to Fetscherin [4], private complaining does not offer the brand a chance to repair failures. In other hand, we use the term public complaining to refer to public act or mass-oriented perspective of private complaining. In digital era, we use the term of electronic word-of-mouth to describe the private complaining trough online channels such as social media and forums [66].

Various papers found a positive relationship between brand hate and negative word-of-mouth [2, 5, 9, 24, 37, 45, 46, 48, 57, 59, 68, 70], private complaining [4, 8, 24], public complaining [4, 6, 8, 68] and electronic word-of-mouth [50, 66].

e) Destruction of brand equity

For companies, brand are the strongest and the most valuable asset [20]. In this spirit, marketers should build a long/strong relationship with consumers [21]. When negative emotions such hate occurs between consumers and a specific brand, harmful behaviors arise leading the destruction of the brand equity. Multiple studies found a negative link between brand hate and brand equity [12, 58].

f) Brand retaliation

Just like the interpersonal hate [16], brand hate leads people to approach the object of hate or retaliate [2]. We refer to brand retaliation as a behavior where consumers trend to cause harm, get even or punish the targeted brand. Fetscherin [4] argue that brand retaliation reflects “*an acute, more impulsive, short-term behavior*”. According to our results, brand hate is an antecedent of brand retaliation [2-5, 24, 37, 48, 51].

g) Brand Revenge

Unlike brand retaliation, brand revenge is more than a “short-term behavior” but a “state-of-mind” where

consumer try to punish the brand in a long-term [4]. It shares the same roots with brand retaliation in causing harm to a brand. Various studies found that brand revenge is a consequence of brand hate [4, 69]

h) Brand boycott

Brand boycott is one of the classic constructs in anti-consumption theory. Consumer boycotting behavior refers to “an effort made by a person or a group of people to achieve particular purposes. Such customers advise others not to buy specific goods or services” [6]. Some scholars believe that brand boycott is a form of proactive revenge where consumers demand compensations of their feelings of loss [6] where others [24] consider it as a form of brand avoidance.

i) Negative brand engagement

Negative brand engagement is usually marginalized construct in marketing literature [9]. According to Hollebeek and Chen [71], brand engagement refers to “level of a consumer’s cognitive, emotional and behavioral investment in specific brand interactions”. The same authors highlight that negative brand engagement occurs when a consumer qualify his experience with a brand as negative, as result a distance is created between them which leads to low level of involvement. Rodrigues, et al. [9] found that brand hate is an antecedent of negative brand engagement.

j) Willingness to make financial sacrifices to hurt the brand (WFS)

This construct was initially used by Fetscherin [4] as antonym to “willingness to make financial sacrifices in order to obtain a brand” which a consequence behavior of brand love. According to the same author, it refers to the situation where “Consumers are willing to spend their own monetary ressource to hurt the brand”. [4]. As construct, it’s based on interdependence theory [72] and it represents multiple differences comparing to brand revenge and brand retaliation [4] because it focuses on monetary aspects rather than harming. Brand hate leads to WFS[4]

4.2. Brand hate in corporate context

The current section deals with brand hate in the corporate context. We will shed a light on different contexts investigated, different industries and most reported hated brands. In addition, we will zoom in brand hate within the brand hate towards luxury brands.

4.2.1. Brand hate in different countries

While analyzing brand hate literature in systematic way, we identify multiple countries where the phenomenon has been studied. We judge that it would be relevant to present these different contexts. We use the term context to refer to the territory where the empirical study has been executed.

Table 2: Contexts investigated in brand hate literature

Study	Sample Size	Context	Measure unit	Most Hated brand
Krishnamurthy and Kucuk [10]	N/A	USA	Anti-brand websites	Microsoft
Bryson, et al. [17]	24	France/UK	Consumers	N/A
Hegner, et al. [2]	244	Germany	Consumers	Apple
Platania, et al. [42]	122	Italy ¹	Consumers	Apple
Hashim and Ahmed [73]	N/A	Pakistan	Consumers	N/A
Kucuk [31]	57	USA	MVB ²	N/A
Zarantonello, et al. [74]	54	Europe	Consumers	N/A
Bryson and Atwal [75]	14	France	Consumers	Starbucks
Fetscherin [4]	712	USA	Consumers	Apple
Hashim and Kasana [43]	255	Pakistan	Consumers	KFC
Islam, et al. [41]	358	Pakistan	Consumers	N/A
Jain and Sharma [66]	147	India	Consumers	N/A
Kucuk [23]	253	USA	Consumers	Apple

¹ 99.2% for the Italian and only 0.8% for the Russian.

² Top 100 Most Valuable Brand

Study	Sample Size	Context	Measure unit	Most Hated brand
Osuna Ramírez, et al. [76]	22	Multinational	Consumers	N/A
Bayarassou, et al. [69]	314	France	Consumers	Bayer- Monsanto
Curina, et al. [68]	265	Italy	Consumers	N/A
Khanna, et al. [77]	200	Pakistan	Consumers	N/A
Kucuk [78]	28	USA	Consumers	N/A
Platania, et al. [79]	422	Italy	Consumers	Nestlé
Sarkar, et al. [80]	339	India	Consumers	Tata
Wisker [81]	392	Malaysia	Consumers	N/A
Zhang and Laroche [24]	1413 ³	USA	Consumers	N/A
Curina, et al. [82]	616	Italy	Consumers	N/A
Husnain, et al. [58]	338	Pakistan	Consumers	Tetra
Itani [11]	397	USA	Consumers	N/A
Joshi and Yadav [50]	374	India	Consumers	N/A
Kashif, et al. [59]	273	Pakistan	Consumers	N/A
Kohli, et al. [83]	250	India	Consumers	N/A
Nguyen and Nguyen [6]	383	Vietnam	Consumers	N/A
Pantano [84]	N/A	N/A	Brand	N/A
Pinto and Brandão [48]	636	Portugal	Consumers	N/A
Rodrigues, et al. [9]	254	International	Consumers	Apple
Wang, et al. [85]	549	Taiwan	Consumers	N/A
Abbasi, et al. [54]	400	Pakistan	Consumers	N/A
Atwal, et al. [86]	N/A	N/A	Brands	N/A
Brandão and Popoli [87]	N/A	N/A	Comments online	N/A
Brandão, et al. [88]	N/A	N/A	Strongest Brands ⁴	Apple
Costa and Azevedo [5]	208	Portugal	Consumers	N/A
Husnain, et al. [89]	233	Pakistan/Saudi Arabia	Consumers	N/A
Jabeen, et al. [51]	342	USA	Consumers	N/A
Kucuk and Aledin [90]	23	USA/Finland	Consumers	N/A
Kurtoğlu, et al. [70]	414	Turkey	Consumers	N/A
Noor, et al. [3]	380	Pakistan	Consumers	N/A
Powell, et al. [91]	485	N/A	Comments	N/A
Roy, et al. [8]	297	USA	Consumers	N/A
Sharma, et al. [57]	208	India	Consumers	Apple
Valenzuela, et al. [92]	69	Chile	Consumers	N/A
Yang and Mundel [44]	562	USA	Consumers	N/A
Rasouli, et al. [93]	815	Iran	Consumers	N/A
Rai, et al. [94]	550	India	Consumers	N/A
Jamal, et al. [95]	1133	Pakistan	Consumers	N/A
Nguyen [37]	358	Vietnam	Consumers	N/A
Bryson, et al. [49]	281	France	Consumers	N/A
Kazmi, et al. [45]	388	Pakistan	Consumers	McDonald
Husnain, et al. [12]	550	Pakistan	Consumers	N/A
Zarantonello, et al. [34]	766 ⁵	Italy/France	Consumers	N/A

³ Sum of 5 studies.

⁴ The 10 strongest brands on the market

⁵ Sum of two studies

Study	Sample Size	Context	Measure unit	Most Hated brand
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Table 2 shows different contexts investigated in brand hate literature and most hated brands of every study. We can interpret this latter (hatred towards Apple, Starbucks and Dolce & Gabbana) in terms of “Negative Double Jeopardy phenomenon” [96] which refers to a situation where a strong brands who generate multiple fans generate stimulatingly brand haters. In addition, contexts like north Africa, middle east and south America are quasi absent in brand hate body of knowledge.

4.2.2. Brand Hate in different industries

Brand hate is widely studied in different industries. We could classify the literature in three different types: Scholars focusing on hate towards specific brands, others towards specific industries and the third kind who studied brand hate in multiple industries. Table 3 presents this taxonomy.

Table 3: Brand Hate in different industries

Taxonomy	Papers
Brand hate towards a specific brand	Starbucks [75], Apple [9], Dolce & Gabbana [86].
Brand hate within a specific industry	Airlines and Hotels [44], Automobile and Cars [80], Cosmetics [50], Dairy products and Fast Moving [12, 58, 77], Fashion Apparel [83], Fast Food [3, 41, 43, 45, 73], Food and OFD [51, 81], Restaurants [11, 93], Services [68], Smart phones [54, 66] and Telecommunications [5, 48, 70].
Brand hate within multiple industries	[2, 4, 10, 23, 31, 42, 57, 69, 74, 76, 79, 82, 85, 92]

Table 3 shows that brand hate is studied towards a specific brand, specific industry, and multiple industries. It is worth signaling that some industries within some countries are the most studied, for example Portuguese researchers focus on the study of brand hatred in the telecommunications industry, while Pakistani researchers have extensively studied brand hatred in the fast-food industry. It is worth highlighting those papers dealing with the phenomenon of brand hate in multiple industry have more impact on literature.

4.2.3. Brand hate in luxury context

Luxury brands have gained the attention of scholars investigating brand hate phenomenon. In this vein, literature demonstrates good predictively of brand hate using three main antecedents: negativestereotypes of luxury brand consumers, customer dissatisfaction with the luxury product or service, and Negative Word Of Mouth [49] and also highlighted brand love can turn to brand hate if the consumers not tolerate a similar value (of luxury brand) is offered to other members of a social group[59]. More recently, Pantano [84] developed novel perspective(burst model) of the way the negative stereotypes exerts negative influence on brand image in the context of a luxury brand aiming to massively increase the sales in a growing market.

4.3. Brand hate outside corporate context

Brand hate phenomenon is studied outside the corporate context. Scholars have investigated it in political market [47], tourism and destination [32, 97], sports and teams [98], education and universities [52] and applications [46]. The current section deals with the findings of this extrapolation of brand hate in these contexts.

4.3.1. Applications-brand hate

Islam, et al. [46] investigated the emotion of hate toward mobile applications. They defined application as “software downloadable to a mobile device which prominently displays a brand identity, often via the name of the app and the appearance of a brand logo or icon, throughout the user experience.” [46]. According to their results, ideological mismatch, symbolic disidentification, and negative experience lead to applications hate. This latter give birth to negative word-of-mouth and brand avoidance. This conclusion is analogous to traditional brand hate body of knowledge.

4.3.2. Universities-brand hate

In Brazilian context, Gois, et al. [52] investigated hatred towards brand of higher educational institutions. According to their study, negative past experience, ideological mismatch, and symbolic incongruence are the main factors of hatred towards educational brands. In addition, Gois, et al. [52] found that female hates

educational brands for ideological issues while male hates it for a poor performance of these brands.

4.3.3. Sports-brand hate

Brand hate is studied also in sports context. [Shuv-Ami, et al. \[98\]](#) developed a scale of ‘love-hate’ within basketball fans, and its antecedents and consequences. Based on mixed emotions theory and social identity theory, [Shuv-Ami, et al. \[98\]](#) found “that the mixed emotions of love for a sports team (in-group) and hatred toward a rival team (out-group) have a significant impact on fans’ behavior.” Their results are aligned with conventional brand hate results [\[11\]](#) that highlight “us against them situation” where consumers fans of certain brand, create their identity by hating the competitor brand.

4.3.4. Tourism and destination brand hate

[Farhat and Chaney \[97\]](#) explored the notion of destination brand hate. In their paper, they concluded that destination brand hate is impacted by negative experience, identity and ideological incongruity and destination policies revealing “us against them” mentality in destination brands. This destination brand hate in turn, leads to behavioral consequences such as negative word-of-mouth and cognitive consequences such as generalization. In their study, one respondent who experience negative emotions towards Germany had negative intention to buy German cars. This finding is in line with brand hate results revealed by [Bryson, et al. \[17\]](#) and [Bryson, et al. \[49\]](#) who indicated that brand hate is related to bad perception of country-of-origin.

4.3.5. Political brand hate

In political market, brand hate is investigated as well. [Banerjee and Goel \[47\]](#) explored the antecedents and consequences of brand hate in political Indian context. According to their results, unmet expectations, ideological incompatibility, and symbolic incongruence leads to hatred towards political brands, which leads to several behaviors such as brand avoidance, brand retaliation and brand extremism.

4.4. Brand hate Trajectories, management, and haters personality

The phenomenon of brand hate has been examined from a dynamic perspective across three key dimensions: its intensity or varying levels, the factors that lead to its emergence, the resulting consequences, and its assessment over time. In addition, literature shows that scholars have focused on two important questions: How companies should deal with brand hate? what are the common personality traits of brand haters? In the current section, we aim to present: Brand hate trajectories; brand hate management and brand haters personality.

4.4.1. Brand hate trajectories

Before introducing brand hate management strategies and exploring haters personality traits, we deem it valuable to examine brand hate from a dynamic standpoint. In other words, how hatred towards a brand is created in emotional terms. It’s worth highlighting that all previous finding reported are based on studies that investigated brand hate in a static perspective.

[Zarantonello, et al. \[74\]](#) investigated how consumers feeling towards a brand change between past, present, and future. According to their findings, there are five trajectories are distinct in shaping brand hate. The first cluster is titled “negative all the way” and describe a scenario where a consumer (active or not) initially had neutral feelings towards a brand, but then negative feelings varying from dislike to hate began to emerge and will persist in future. “Down-up” is the second cluster which describes “a situation where the feeling for the brand has now dropped, but may pick up again in the future.” [\[74\]](#). The third type of trajectories is nominated “Downward slope flattens” which describe a consumer-brand relationship starting from a very positive emotions to end up at a very dark emotions that will continue in the future; this type can be viewed in lens of [Grégoire, et al. \[13\]](#) statement “when customer love turns into lasting hate”. The “roller coaster” is the fourth possible trajectory under which a consumer used to have a natural relationship, which then evolved into a very positive relationship before degrading into extremely negative feelings. The last trajectory is “Steady decrease” type indicating a 360° evolution of relationship starting from brand love to end in brand hate. it is important to note that, these trajectories are not gender specific [\[74\]](#). Besides the emotional changes in consumer-brand relationship, [Zarantonello, et al. \[74\]](#) reveal that negative past experience is associated with three trajectories of brand hate namely “Down-ward slope flattens”, “Down-up” and “Steady decrease”, while corporate wrongdoing (ideological incompatibility) is associated with “Negative all the way” and symbolic incongruence triggers “Roller coaster”.

Overall brand hate is a dynamic concept that dependent on reasons behind it and when it had occurred. This complexity give birth to practical question related to its management. In the following section, we will discuss how companies should manage brand hate ?

4.4.2. Brand hate management

Brand hate management refers to brand recovery strategies advanced by the literature. Besides investigating antecedents and consequences of brand hate, and apprehending the phenomenon in dynamic way, some authors [73] focused on how brands can deal with brand hate. The subject of this section is to present these strategies.

Hashim and Ahmed [73] tested the impact of “Apology, compensation and explanation” strategies advanced by Kucuk [1] as moderator between brand hate and brand recovery. Using an experimental research design, the authors revealed that the combination of these strategies is the best mean to manage brand hate towards fast food chains in Pakistan. In separate terms, compensation of losses resulting of a negative experience is the second powerful intervention followed by apology while explanation have no significant effect.

Yang and Mundel [44] are aligned with the previous finding related to compensation mechanism. The explain “monetary compensation was an effective feedback strategy in restoring consumer satisfaction” [44].

Overall, the diversity of brand hate management strategies is related to its complexity as phenomenon vue the multiple antecedents found. A steam of research [1, 5, 82] believe that the consumer personality plays a crucial role in brand hate equation. Kucuk (2019, p66) noted that “Although company-related factors play very important role in creating brand hate, some of the brand hate might have nothing to do with the company but rather with consumer him/herself”. In the following section, we will explore the brand hater’s personality.

4.4.3. Brand hater’s personality

Curina, et al. [82] classify brand haters based on multiple criteria : level of brand hate, industry of the hated brand, brand hate antecedents and brand hate outcomes. According to their cluster analysis, four types of haters are found. “Forgiving profile” “is the first cluster that experience a low level of brand hate towards clothing and accessories operators with no significant antecedents or behavioral outcomes. “Indifferent profile” experiences a Intermediate level of hate towards brand of accessories and clothing based generally of their negative experience with these brands and trend to avoid them as reaction. The third cluster is nominated “Bad influencer” with a high level towards technology and telecommunication brands industry, their hate is based on negative experience while their reaction trend to negative negatively other consumers. The fourth and the most extreme cluster is “radical haters”, that experience a maximum level towards fast food brand for ideological and identity mismatch reasons. Their reaction is more intense than avoidance or negative influence, it tends to brand retaliation and public complaining.

Another taxonomy of brand haters is advanced by Costa and Azevedo [5] who studied the ability of telecommunications of Portuguese brand haters to forgive their operators. Their finding show that female have a low level of brand hate and higher willingness to forgive their brands (female forgivers), mainstream Haters (composed of male and female) experience a medium level of brand hate but a love level of forgiveness and Male heavy brand haters with a maximum level of brand hate and the lowest score of potential forgiveness.

5. Methodologies and Methods

The current section deals with methodologies used in brand hate literature. It will provide details about research methodologies, methods and instruments used to apprehend this phenomenon.

5.1. Methodologies

The present section investigates the research approach found in brand hate literature. It includes the usage of quantitative, qualitative, mixed and experimental methodologies.

5.1.1. Quantitative methodology

From the analysis of literature, it can be understood that survey methodology has been the most significantly used in brand hate research stream. The main advantage of it is obtaining large samples, with very less investment and are comparatively easy to generalize the results of any given study. Though surveys only provide estimates of the true population and not exact measurements[99], they still help in facilitating an understanding of the information about attitudes or perceptions at large. Though there are several advantages one of the primary disadvantages is surveys are not perfect devices to collect data, as surveys require respondents to recollect past behavior which may not always be accurate[100]. Out of 62 empirical studies 40 used survey method to collect data.

In addition to survey methods grounded on primary data, secondary data is also used in brand hate body of knowledge. Kucuk [31] used secondary data regarding the most valuable brands in his study.

5.1.2. Qualitative methodology

Qualitative methodology is the second most used approach in brand hate literature (n=11). It is used generally to explore or reveal critical in-depth actionable insights it generates. In terms of methods, interviews are most used method in brand hate literature. Followed by netnography with a focus on consumers reviews and comments online and study cases of certain brands (Dolce & Gabbana). Only one study used focus groups to apprehend the phenomenon of brand hate. [92].

5.1.3. Mixed methodology

Some authors used mixed methodology to study brand hate in order to gain advantages of both methodologies (n=5). This usage differed from study to another, for example Bryson and Atwal [75] used a short survey to detect the most hated brand in France followed by semi structured interviews to explore the reasons and behaviors of hatred towards Starbucks. Another example of mixed method is Husnain, et al. [89]'s paper who used interviews and survey to understand the mechanism of brand embarrassment, brand hate and brand detachment.

5.1.4. Experimental Methodology

Experimental methodology is also used to understand brand hate (n=4). This methodology is used with two main focus: Management of brand hate [44, 73] or explanation of brand hate process [66, 81]. Another pattern concluded is total correlation between the usage of experimental methods and specification of the industry studied.

5.2. Methods

Beside the methodologies used, multiple analysis methods and modeling methods are found. Structural equation modeling is the most used in brand hate literature. This can be understandable when we keep in mind that this "second generation of multivariate analysis" is a coupling between psychometric and econometric perspective used to demonstrates the relationship between latent variables measures trough observables variables (items). Two methods are found in our analysis: SEM-PLS (n=16) and SEM-CB (n=19). Regression methods are also found in brand hate literature (n=9), while ANOVA, ANCOVA and ANCOVA methods are used generally with experimental methods (n=3). Cluster analyses are also used in cases of detecting a pattern or regrouping sub-sample sharing same characteristics (n=3). From non-numeric cases, content analysis is the single method used (n=10).

6. Theories and frameworks

Contrasted to other literature reviews related to brand hate [14, 18, 101], the current section aims to explain the usage of multiple theories found in brand hate literature.

As we mentioned before, the triangular theory of hate [16] is widely used to explain the emotional components of brand hate and clarify its nature. When it comes to antecedents, multiple frameworks and theories are mobilized. Self-congruity [39] theory is the most used in this vein, for example constructs like functional or symbolic incongruence are derived from it. For this later, some authors [43, 54] explaining it referring to Disidentification theory which stipulates that *"to create self-concepts, people try to disidentify themselves from the brand that has an undesired image which is inconsistent with their personality."* [43]. Negative past experience as construct find its roots in expectancy violation theory [102] and social contract theory [44]. Ideological incompatibility find its origin in avoidance model advanced by Lee, et al. [36] while subjective norms, as construct, is related to the theory of planned behavior [56] as we explained before. Other theories are also used to justify brand hate antecedents in social level, for example social identity theory [103] is mobilized to explain why certain consumers "in group" can develop hate toward brands used by others consumers "out group". Antecedents related to counter effects of adverting are generally viewed in lens of Hierarchy of effects theory [104] and elaboration likelihood model [105] according to which "If the (brand) message aligns with one's values and beliefs, it will be perceived as positive and vice versa" [81].

Behaviors resulting of brand hate are viewed in lens of "voice or exit" theory [106]. According to which negative relationship between a consumer and brand can lead to two possible options: "voice strategy" where consumer express their dissatisfaction towards brand and this expression can take multiple manifestations based on their level of hate; "exit strategy" where consumer cut his relationship with the brand.

Additional theories are used to explain other aspects of brand hate. For example stimulus-organism-response model [107] is used to identify the relationship between antecedents (stimulus), brand hate (organism) and it consequences (response). Traits personality models such as big five and agency-communion models are also used to explain brand haters personalities [23].

7. Conclusion, Future research directions

In conclusion, the literature on brand hate provides valuable insights into the emotional and behavioral responses of consumers toward brands. Brand hate, characterized by intense negative emotions, has been shown to result from various antecedents such as negative experiences, ideological mismatches, and symbolic incongruence. Its outcomes range from brand avoidance and switching to negative word-of-mouth and brand retaliation. Researchers have employed a variety of methodologies, including surveys, qualitative approaches, mixed methods, and experiments, to explore this complex phenomenon. While theories like the triangular theory of hate and self-congruity have shed light on the nature of brand hate. Overall, the brand hate literature continues to evolve, offering opportunities for deeper understanding and practical implications for businesses and brands. Furthermore, based on our systematic review, we draw possible and promising avenues for future research.

In terms of theoretical assumptions, scholars should use other lens to apprehend the nature of brand hate such as Opotow [108] and Opotow and McClelland [109], in addition there a call of investigation of the second theory of duplex theory of hate [16] which is "Hate as story".

In terms of industries, research have mainly focus on B2C context without investigating the nature of brand hate in B2B context. In addition, another area of research is exploring brand hate in distributor brand context. As the study of brand hate has been extrapolated to other contexts, it will be interesting to investigate brand hated towards employer brand. Future research could also challenge brand hate in industries like banks and assurances. Other geographical contexts like Africa, middle east and south America should be investigated as well. In addition, comparative studies remain very limited. An investigation of brand hate theory in Mediterranean area could be beneficial as long as this space contains three continents and different cultures.

From a methodological point of view, it's crucial to move from traditional survey methods to machine learning based methods. For data collection, research should use more secondary data in order to overcome the limits of primary data. Another future research area is cross-cultural and cross-country studies, as highlighted before, in order to underline the role of cultural and ideological characteristics in shaping brand hate. In a methodic level, it would be interesting to use other unit measure such as marketing specialists to develop strategies to deal with brand hate.

Management of brand hate is one of the main underrated topics in literature. Hashim and Ahmed [73] studied how to manage brand hate resulting of negative experience in fast food industry, future research should investigate brand hate resulting of other antecedents.

Last, but not least, dependance techniques are dominating brand hate literature. However, it would be beneficial to use other approaches such as semiotics analysis as revealed by Kucuk [1].

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